

A Solitary Giant Preputial Calculus in an Uncircumcised Adolescent Presenting with Acute Urinary Obstruction: A Case Report

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Abstract

Background

Preputial calculi are a very rare urological condition, typically associated with phimosis and poor genital hygiene. Their occurrence in adolescents is uncommon, and large solitary stones causing acute urinary obstruction are particularly rare.

Case-Presentation

We report a 19-year-old uncircumcised male presenting with a five-day history of progressive difficulty in urination. Examination revealed a non-retractile prepuce with a palpable hard mass. A diagnosis of preputial calculus was made clinically. The patient underwent dorsal slit followed by circumcision, resulting in the removal of a solitary large calculus measuring approximately 5.8 cm. Recovery was uneventful, with complete resolution of symptoms.

Conclusion

Although rare, preputial calculi should be considered in uncircumcised patients presenting with obstructive urinary symptoms. Early surgical intervention is curative and prevents complications.

Introduction

A preputial stone is a very rare form of urinary tract stone, which only occurs in a small number of individuals who are not circumcised, with poor genital hygiene, phimosis, and low socioeconomic conditions. It can occur at any age range, from 5 to 92 years(1). It is defined as the accumulation of calcified debris in the preputial sac. It was first reported by Robert Clarke in 1794(2). Preputial calculi are rare entities in urological practice, most commonly reported in elderly individuals with long-standing phimosis, poor hygiene, and urinary stasis. Their development is attributed to the accumulation of smegma, deposition of urinary salts, or a combination of both.

Cases in adolescents are extremely rare, and the presence of a large solitary calculus leading to acute urinary obstruction is unusual. Due to their rarity, such cases may be misdiagnosed or overlooked.

This report describes a rare case of a giant preputial calculus measuring 5.8 cm by 5.8 cm in a 19-year-old male presenting with acute urinary obstruction, highlighting the importance of early recognition and management.

Case Presentation

A 19-year-old male presented with a five-day history of progressive difficulty in urination, characterized by straining and a sensation of incomplete bladder emptying. There was no history of fever, hematuria, trauma, or prior urological procedures. The patient had childhood traumatic injury of foreskin related to his trial of cutting it. Due to this reason, he progressively had been developing phimosis for so long time, which leads to the formation the calculus.

The patient was uncircumcised and reported poor genital hygiene.

On physical examination:

- The prepuce was hugely distended and non-retractile (phimosis)
- A firm, non-tender, palpable mass was noted within the preputial sac ([Figure2&3](#))
- Mild suprapubic fullness was present

Vital signs were stable. Laboratory investigations were largely unremarkable. Radiography of the genitalia shows a circular, solitary radio-opaque mass inside the prepuce ([Figure 1](#)).

A clinical diagnosis of preputial calculus causing bladder outlet obstruction was made.

Figure 1: A radiograph of the genitalia showing a giant, solitary preputial calculus

Figure 2: A large, globular, and firm preputial mass in a 19-year-old adolescent

Figure 3: Clinical presentation of a large, smooth, well-circumscribed preputial mass in an uncircumcised adolescent

Management and Outcome

The patient underwent a dorsal slit procedure under local anesthesia. Upon exposure, a single large calculus was identified within the preputial sac and removed (Figure 4). This was followed by definitive circumcision.

The extracted calculus was:

- Solitary
- Yellowish-brown
- Hard in consistency
- Approximately **5.8 cm** in maximum diameter and weighs 250 grams (Figure 5)

Postoperatively, the patient had immediate relief of urinary symptoms. Recovery was uneventful, and he was discharged on the second postoperative day. At two-week follow-up, the surgical site had healed well, and the patient reported normal urinary function.

Figure 4: Phimosis with a visible giant preputial stone in a 19-year-old adolescent

Figure 5: A giant, solitary, globular, and yellowish-brown calculus measuring 5.8 x 5.8 cm after extraction

Discussion

Preputial calculi are rare and are typically classified into three types:

1. Smegma-derived calculi
2. Urinary salt calculi
3. Mixed-type calculi

The pathogenesis involves chronic retention of smegma due to phimosis, combined with urinary stasis and possible infection, leading to crystallization and stone formation. In our case, the smegma solidification was the possible pathogenetic cause, as the phimosis was not severe enough to cause urinary stasis and salt precipitation(3). In addition, this process could explain the reason why local infection was encountered. The clinical features range from asymptomatic swelling to acute urinary obstruction. Diagnosis is usually clinical but can be supported by imaging when necessary.

While most reported cases occur in elderly or debilitated individuals, this case demonstrates that adolescents are also at risk, particularly in the presence of poor hygiene and untreated phimosis. Compared to previous reports (4, 5), the current case is unique in terms of the stone size and age at presentation. This case was a 19-year-old adolescent who came with a complaint of difficulty urinating for five days. Upon physical examination, his general appearance was stable. BP = 110/70 mmhg PR= 80 bpm, To = 36 degree Celsius. He had mild suprapubic tenderness. The bladder wasn't distended. The patient had a non-tender, globular, wet meatal region, smooth-surface, and hard-consistency preputial sac mass. On plain radiography of the pelvis, there was a circular radio-opaque foreign body over the preputial sac. We scanned the upper urinary tract with ultrasound, but there was nothing higher up.

Coming to treatment, the patient was taken into the operating theatre and underwent a dorsal slit procedure for circumcision under local anesthesia, and then the stone was removed. Circumcision not only facilitates stone removal but also prevents recurrence by eliminating the preputial space. Postoperatively, the patient was in good condition and functioned normally. However, delayed treatment may result in complications such as infection, ulceration, fistula formation, and, rarely, malignancy.

Conclusion

This case highlights a rare presentation of a solitary giant preputial calculus in an adolescent. Clinicians should consider this diagnosis in uncircumcised patients presenting with obstructive urinary symptoms. Early surgical management is effective and prevents complications.

Ethics Statement

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying clinical details. Institutional ethical approval was not required for a single case report under local guidelines.

Consent for Publication

The patient provided written informed consent for publication of anonymized clinical information.

Data Availability Statement

All relevant data are within the manuscript. No additional datasets were generated or analyzed.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare that no competing interests exist.

Author Contributions

- Conceptualization: Fekadie Amare
- Data curation: Fekadie Amare
- Investigation: Fekadie Amare
- Methodology: Fekadie Amare
- Writing – original draft: Fekadie Amare

- Writing – review & editing: Fekadie Amare, Seifeyared Abebaw

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References

1. Palinrungi MA, Kholis K, Syahrir S, Faruk M. Multiple preputial stones: A case report and literature review. *International Journal of Surgery Case Reports*. 2020;70:87-92.
2. Surya D, Gharde P, Reddy K. Preputial calculus: unveiling a rare encounter and treatment journey. *Cureus*. 2024;16(4).
3. Symeonidis EN, Toutziaris C, Katsimantas A, Dimitriadis G. Incidental detection of preputial calculus in a patient with partial phimosis: is it as rare as we believed? *Acta medica Lituanica*. 2021;28(1):195.
4. Murugan B, Das S. Phimosis presenting with preputial calculus: a case report on an uncommon presentation of a common condition. *Cureus*. 2021;13(1).
5. Chong TH, Asyraf MZ, Hayati F, Azizan N, Sahid NA, Ting JRS, et al. Giant preputial calculus: The first reported case in Malaysia. *Case reports in surgery*. 2018;2018(1):4606259.